

NFDI4Objects
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

Vom Ogham-Stein zum FAIR/LO(U)D Digital Object

Wie Gigha Brewing und der
federated Knowledge Graph
historische Artefakte lebendig machen

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AG CAA | 25-26 Sep 2025 | Köln | Germany | 25/09/2025

FAIR

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

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via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data (LOD) is the method of choice for linking data and FAIRification ...

... to feed the federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem.

Die digitale Transformation archäologischer Kulturgüter ermöglicht neue Formen der wissenschaftlichen Vernetzung und zeigt, wie archäologische Artefakte Einfluss auf heutige Communities nehmen.

Beispiel: Der Ogham-Stein CIIC 506 (GIGHA/1) auf der Isle of Gigha

GIGHA/1

Corpus Refs: [Macalister/1945:506](#)

Site: [GIGHA](#)

Discovery: first mentioned, 1873 White, T.P.

History: Forsyth/1996, 288: 'not until the latter half of the nineteenth [century] was any mention made of the ogham inscription [the stone itself having been known since the seventeenth century]. The first to submit the inscription to critical examination was a party from the Royal Society of Antiquaries of Ireland, who, on the recommendation of Rhys, included the stone in their 1899 archaeological tour of the Scottish Islands. ... The stone has fallen and been re-erected at least twice. The first recorded fall came in about 1843-4 when the stone was toppled 'by some young men for their own amusement'. The piece that broke off the top as a result of the incident was incorporated into a nearby pigsty, and subsequently into the masonry of new houses built on the site. ... After the fall, on the instructions of the landowner, the stone was dragged back to the top of the hillock and re-erected on its old site 'with great care'. It was fixed in place by a mason, but, because the hillock had been quarried on one side, towards the base of the stone, it fell again some twenty years later, i.e. c. 1864. According to local witnesses the condition of the stone was not impaired by the second fall. Rather than re-erect it precisely on the original site, the new owner ordered it be replaced 'at a very short distance'.

Geology: Forsyth/1996, 290: 'Granite'. Macalister/1945, 484: 'Slaty grit'.

Dimensions: 1.7 x 0.25 x 0.31 (Forsyth/1996)

Setting: in ground

Location: on site

Forsyth/1996, 28: 'Though this is not the original location of the stone, according to local tradition, it is very close to it'.

Form: plain

Forsyth/1996, 290: 'A tall, four-sided pillar'.

Condition: complete , poor

Forsyth/1996, 290: 'Poor...In addition to general weathering, there are a number of more specific injuries, large, shallow, unevenly spaced chunks missing from the ogham-bearing arris'.

Folklore: none

Crosses: none

Decorations: no other decoration

References

- [Fisher/2001](#) 117 photo concise discussion
- [Forsyth/1996](#) 288–291 photo concise discussion
- [Macalister/1945](#) 484 concise discussion

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via http://w3id.org/cispdb/stone/gigha_1

GIGHA/1/1

Readings

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): VICULAMAQ CUGINI

Expansion:

VICULA MAQ CUGINI

[Macalister/1945](#) 484 reading only

Forsyth, K.S. (1996): VIC[[I]ULA MAQ[U]]T[[I]O[M]]GI[L]U]]

Expansion:

V[[I]]U[L]A MAQ[U]] [C][I]O[M]G[I[N]]I]]

[Forsyth/1996](#) 291–298 substantial discussion

Notes

Orientation: vertical up

Position: inc ; arris ; inc ; undecorated

Incision: inc

Date: 600 - (RCAHMS/1971)

Jackson in RCAHMS/1971, 96: 'perhaps not older than the 7th century'.

400 - 599 (Forsyth/1996)

Forsyth/1996, 297, suggests that Jackson's date may be too late, arguing that 'the final vowels -*li* u and -*i* may indeed be present and thus the text need not post-date apocope'.

Language: Goidelic (ogham)

Ling. Notes: Forsyth/1996, 291–297 persuasively argues for seeing this stone as the product of a goidelic milieu.

Palaeography: Forsyth/1996, 295: 'Gigha is written in the classic ... Ogham with no drawn stem-line and vowels which are little more than nicks - the 'text-book' form of the script'.

Legibility: poor

Forsyth/1996, 292: 'The first six letters are extremely doubtful'.

Lines: 1

Carving errors: 0

Doubtful: no

Names

- [Vicula](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of Macalister/1945, 484.
- [Cugini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of Macalister/1945, 484.
- [Viqua](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of Forsyth/1996, 296.
- [\[C\]o\[m\]g\[i\]n\[i\]](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
This is the reading of Forsyth/1996.

via <https://github.com/LinkedOpenOgham/cisp-recovery>

main 1 Branch 0 Tags Go to file Code

Rorlanthary Delete CNAME 37 days 2 months ago 24 Comments

doc/cisp Delete CNAME 2 months ago

README.md Update README.md 2 months ago

cisp-recovery

Recovery repository for the data on <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/>.

W3ID PIDs

Three entities got W3ID PIDs, examples are as follows:

- stone : http://w3id.org/cispdb/stone/abcar_1 for ABCAR/1
- site : <http://w3id.org/cispdb/site/abcar> for Aberc
- name : <http://w3id.org/cispdb/namespace/peter>

Search via Parameter

- [...]/cisp/database?id=26,187 --> KWDR/3
- [...]/cisp/database?cisp-class/1/1 --> CLMG/1/1

UCL

404 - Error page not found

This page could not be found.

GIGHA/1 Ogham Stone in der CISP (recovery) Database

Er wurde nicht nur wissenschaftlich dokumentiert, sondern prägt heute sichtbar die lokale Identität.

This tells us that **Lait(h)** = Ale, the stuff consumed copiously in Northern society at this season, plus **Ir** = killed.

So **Latheirt** means “ale-killed”, ale has killed us.

The rather unimaginative translator adds that the Latin meaning is **crapula**, or “drunkenness”

– Roger Pearse

O'D guesses 'a threadbare cloak': but cf. W. *Humnan* 'a banner'. O'Clery has *lomain* i. *brat* 'mantle'.—Ed.

LATHERT ['drunkenness'] i.e. *lait(h)* 'ale' and *irt* 'death' to him who drank it: [*var. lectio*] i.e. the drinking of beer or ale killed him.

lathirt (gl. c)rapula) *Ir. Glosses*, No. 286. *lait(h)* = Corn. *lad* (gl. liquor), *Lat. latex*.—Ed.

LUOBORT ('a herb-garden') melius est (i.e. *lath-gort* i.e. *gort lath* 'a garden of vegetables').

luobort Lib. Arm. 17 b. 1: *luobortoir* (gl. olitor) Z. 45. Corn. *luworth*, *lowarth*, *Br. liorz*.—*lath* = AS. *leof*, Obg. *laub*, and *gort* = *χρῶρον*, *hortus*. This gloss can hardly have been written in the tenth century.—Ed.

LÍN ('flax') a *lino*. *Léine* ('a shirt') a *linceo* one from another. Now *lios*, *Manx lioen*, W. and Bret. *lhin*.—Ed.

LÁNOMAIN ('a married couple') i. *lánshomáin* full property of each other, for each is half property without the other

B adds: Aliter *lanamain* quasi *lanamain* ('clinging') ar ni fil etarecard doib acht ar dia ('for there is no sundering of them save for God's sake'); *lánamain* 'matrimonium' Z. 988,989.—Ed. *Manx lannoon* 'a couple'.—Ed.

Ogham gloss that reads in Irish **Latheirt**, i.e. **massive hangover**.

By **Katherine Forsyth**, OG(H)AM UK Principal Investigator

Any of you participating in the 'Dry January' challenge will, I hope, forgive this month's featured ogham. It comes courtesy of a microbrewery on the Isle of Gigha which declares itself 'dedicated to crafting unique, small-batch beers that capture the essence of this stunning Hebridean island. ... every pint is a love letter to this special place.' That letter is written in the ogham alphabet, of course!

Gigha Brewery are proud of the island's wonderful ogham pillar which we were delighted to visit and record back in 2022 when we acquired these bottles – for purely scientific purposes 🧐. There is a separate section on their [website](#) dedicated to ogham – the only brewery in the world to be so distinguished – and the script also features on their product labels. Ogham is not so easy on a smooth, round bottle (though there are ways!), and they employ a drawn-in stem-line, but the script is otherwise classic. They even use the first forid (X) in its oldest value: /k/ to represent the first letter of their top-brewed 'Kölsch'-style beer.

As you can see, the ogham is used to represent the English names of their beers and, as often happens with modern use of ogham mediated via the Web, the letters are rather widely spaced. They could all be slightly closer together, especially in G-O-L-D-E-N A-L-E where there are no two successive letters from the same *aicme* (group). So, there is no room for confusion – exactly as the script was planned to ensure.

Og(h)am of the Month Jan 2025: S-ARL-001 (CIIC 506 | GIGHA/1)

Ogham as part of the local heritage and brewery identity

Ogham

What is Ogham

What is Ogham?

Other than on our bottle designs, Ogham is an Early Medieval script used primarily to write the early Irish language, and later the Old Irish language. There are roughly 400 surviving orthographic inscriptions on stone monuments throughout Ireland and western Britain, the bulk of which are in southern Munster.

Corpus

Monumental ogham inscriptions are found in Ireland and Wales, with a few additional specimens found in south-west England (Devon and Cornwall), the Isle of Man, and Scotland, including Shetland and a single example from Sicily in England. They were mainly employed as territorial markers and memorials (grave stones). The stone commemorating Vortiporus, a 5th-century king of Dyfed (originally located in Cymdeirion), is the only ogham stone inscription that bears the name of an identifiable individual. The language of the inscriptions is predominantly Primitive Irish, the few inscriptions in Scotland, such as the Lunnainn stone, record fragments of what is probably the Pictish language.

The more ancient examples are standing stones, where the script was carved into the edge (drom or faobhar) of the stone, which formed the stemline against which individual characters are cut. The text of these "orthodox Ogham" inscriptions is read beginning from the bottom left-hand side of a stone, continuing upwards along the edge across the top and down the right-hand side (in the case of long inscriptions). Roughly 300 inscriptions are known in total (a number, incidentally, very close to the number of known inscriptions in the contemporary Gaelic dialects) of which the earliest concentration by far is found in the

The Ogham stone on Gigha

Situated just west of the ruins of Kishbatten Church, is the Cnoc A'Chomaidh (hill of the Piles) on which stands the inscribed Ogham Stone. This pillar is square in section, standing five feet nine inches from the ground and measuring 3 feet 3 inches in circumference at the top. Throughout the years it has received a fair amount of knocks, and the weathering on the exposed side has made it difficult to get a perfect transcription of the original sculpturing. However Professor R. A. Macalister has given the reading as 'NOLLA MACH CROIBHE' - 'NOLLA SON OF CROIBHE' - and holds the opinion that it is a Scottish inscription cut under Pictish influence. Although there are other suggestions as to the meaning of the words, it is a grave-stone with the conventional type of inscription giving the name of the deceased and that of his father, and probably dates from the earliest settlements of the Scots in Galloway.

Gighas Ogham Stone

Following the launch of trove.scot in February 2025 we are now planning the retiral of some of our web services. Canmore will be switched off on 24th June 2025. Information about the closure can be found on the HES website: [Retiral of HES web services](#) | [Historic Environment Scotland](#)

Map

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Ogham Stone located on the Isle of Gigha / Giogha

CANMORE
NATIONAL RECORD OF THE HISTORIC ENVIRONMENT

Part of Historic Environment Scotland

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Gigha, Cnoc Na Carraigh

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- MyCanmore Text

Ogham Inscribed Stone (Early Medieval), Standing Stone (Prehistoric)

Site Name Gigha, Cnoc Na Carraigh
Classification Ogham Inscribed Stone (Early Medieval), Standing Stone (Prehistoric)
Canmore ID 38529
Site Number NR64NW 2
NGR NR 6426 4817
Datum OSGB36 - NGR
Permalink <http://canmore.org.uk/site/38529>

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Correction Favourite

1:10,000 Quarter Sheet	NR 64 NW	2	OS No.	STRATHCLYDE	New Dist COUNTY	ARGYLL	TYPE	2 3 4	V Page 1
NGR NR 6426 4817	CE	Dist No.	ARGYLL & BUTE	DIST PAR	GIGHA & CARA	FORM	STANDING STRUCTURE	PERIOD	INCOMPLETE
Definition Record No. Ref.	SCHEDULED		STATUS Date of Issue	Inscribed Stone (NR) (Ogam) [NAT]					
SITE NAME AND MAIN FEATURES CNOC NA CARRAIGH, GIGHA Ogam-inscribed Standing Stone (NR 64274818) Standing Stone (NR).							1. OS 6" 1924 2. RCAHM Kintyre 1971 96-7 No 244 Illust. Visited 1966 a. A Description of the Western Islands of Scotland 1934 263 (M Martin) b. JRS&I 31 1901 18ff		
The Ogam inscription is defaced by a series of holes on the base-line, but Professor K H Jackson suggests, very tentatively, that it may have read 'the son of Coicéille'							S614 S082 = 3 Rlys 1901 = Bibm. 26627		

<https://canmore.org.uk/collection/2415903>

The Ogham Stone is well-documented in CANMORE

Linked Open Ogham Stones

... creating Linked Open Data

images: Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Me & my Dad in Ireland ...

... looking for Ogham Stones ... !

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

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The Linked Open Ogham LOD / Wikidata Workflow

Extract from the Linked Open Ogham Ontology

Ogham

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Ogham Stone located on the Isle of Gigha / Giogha

Photograph by Megan Kasten / OG(H)AM Project / University of Glasgow

THE OGHAM AND ANALOGOUS INSCRIPTIONS OF SCOTLAND.¹

COUNTY OF ARGYLL.

506.—Gigha.

1899, *JRSAI* 29 : 345. 1901, *JRSAI* 31 : 18 (Rhys) 440 (Macalister). 1926, *Scottish Gaelic Studies* 1 : 3 (F. C. Diack).

On the top of a knoll overlooking the village, on the side of the island of Gigha facing the mainland : now protected by a wooden fence. (It is easily visible from the mainland when the spectator knows where to look for it). Slaty grit, 6' 8" × 0' 10" × 0' 8½". Inscription cut and rubbed on the

N.W. angle, and now worn and in very bad condition : the sides of the stone show frets of vertical and horizontal lines, which are evidently modern additions. The inscription reads :

VICULA MAQ CUGINI

The first C is not to be resolved into DD. The angle at 1U is broken, and this letter might be an O. The following letter is certainly L, though in some aspects of the stone it looks like S : L² and M run into one another. There is a hole 2½" across in the edge between the M and the following A, and in the opposite edge there is a similar hole corresponding to it : the first of these, at least, must have been on the stone before the inscription was cut, as the lapidary passed it over. A triangular flake has been broken away from the H-surface between the Q and 2C, but apparently without injuring the inscription. 2U is faint though traceable, but the final I can only be guessed at.

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p. 484

Ogham Stone located on the Isle of Gigha / Giogha

via <https://github.com/guariento/og-h-am/blob/main/XML/S-ARL/S-ARL-001.xml>

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  <idno type="CISP">GIGHA/1</idno>
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  </availability>
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    <msIdentifier>
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      <repository/>
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            <depth>0.31 at base, 0.23 at the top</depth>
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        </supportDesc>
        <condition>A tall, square-shaped pillar, it <q>is unclear whether the monument is a re-used pre-historic standing stone or a pillar specially erected for the bearing of the inscription</q> (Forsyth 1996, 289). <q>The stone has fallen and been re-erected at least twice</q>; the first time it was intentionally toppled by some young men while the second fall was as a result of quarrying near the base on one side of the stone (ibid. 288-289). There is general weathering with <q>a series of four large, shallow, unevenly spaced chunks missing from the ogham-bearing aris</q> (ibid. 290). The ogham inscription <q>which is worn and in bad condition, is defaced by series of spalls - the aris</q> (ibid. 290). The portion of the inscription <q>nearest the ground is the most badly worn and the most disputed</q> (ibid. 291).
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      </objectDesc>
      <layoutDesc>
        <layout style="vertical" rend="arris_up">The ogham inscription is on the north west edge of the four-sided pillar stone and reads upwards from the bottom.
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      <objectDesc>
        <handDesc>
          <handNote>There is a wide range of published interpretations of the ogham that along with its general poor condition make a definitive reading difficult. On the same grounds, it is difficult to make definitive statements about its carving technique. <q>As they now survive, the strokes are finger-scale and with a U-section, where it can be measured with any certainty the length of h-acute strokes is about <math>40\text{--}60\text{mm}</math></q> (Forsyth 1996, 291). The gaps between the letters most likely contained vowel notches now lost. Forsyth (ibid. 295) describes the ogham inscription as <q>ogham with no drawn stem-line and vowels which are little more than nicks - the 'text-book' form of the script</q>.
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      </handDesc>
    </physDesc>
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      <provenance type="found" when="1873">Formerly the middle stone of a straight alignment of three stones known locally as the 'Clocks of Gigha'. The ogham stone is located on a hillock, <placeName>Cnoc na Carraigh ('hill of the rock')</placeName>, about 90 m NW of the ruined chapel of Kilchattan on the island of <placeName>Gigha</placeName>. Although the stone has been noted since <date>1695</date>, the inscription was not noticed until <date>1873</date>.
      </provenance>
      <provenance type="observed" when="2022-09-14">Visited and recorded in situ in 2022.
      </provenance>
    </history>
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E22

E25

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

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  </ab>
</div>
<div type="apparatus">
  <listApp>
    <app n="1">
      <note>As Forsyth notes <q>The first six letters are extremely doubtful</q>. For the portion of the inscription closest to the ground, the indentations of strokes <q>can be clearly felt on the arbris, but the lines are too indistinct to interpret</q> (1996, 292). From the seventh character onwards the carving is clearer and there is greater agreement amongst previous editors (ibid. 293).</note>
    </app>
    <app n="2">
      <note>Rhys (1899) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1899">
        MAQICAGILEB
      </rdg>
    </app>
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      <note>Rhys (1901, 18-23) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1901">
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    </app>
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        VICULA MAQ COMGINI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="5">
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      <rdg resp="MAC1945">
        VICULA MAQ CUGINI
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        VIDDOOSAMO QICOGINI
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    <!--<app n="7">
      <note>Jackson (1971, 96-97) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="JAC1971">
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        H\.\JMAQT/cAGII/bb
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    </listApp>
  </div>
  <div type="translation">
    <p>According to Forsyth (1996, 297), Jackson offered <q>a very hypothetical</q> interpretation: the son of <persName>Coicéile</persName> (see <ref target="https://canmore.org.uk/event/695592">Canmore</ref>).</p>
  </div>
  <div type="commentary">
    <p><q>If the letters before the M are not admitted then the formula 'MAQ-X' is likely, either as 'the son of X', or more likely, as a compound name with first element MAQ (Forsyth 1996, 296)</q> However, Forsyth maintains that there is sufficient evidence for the existence of some ogham carvings before the letter M which consequently implies that Gigha 1 conforms to the Irish formula 'X son of Y'.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 297) also rejects Macalister's suggestion for VICULA as <foreign xml:lang="sga">Fiacal</foreign> meaning 'tooth' on the grounds that <q>OIr ia is from earlier e, both long and short i remained as i</q>. Meanwhile the second name COMGINI is interpreted by Macalister as OIR <persName xml:lang="sga">Coemgen</persName>, which Forsyth comments is a <q>widespread and well-known male name (<foreign xml:lang="sga">Coem</foreign> <ref target="https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007550019000000">Coem</ref> </foreign> + <foreign xml:lang="sga">gen</foreign> 'Fair born' (Uhllich 1993:2071), found variously spelled, including <persName xml:lang="ga">Comganiz</persName></q>.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 296) is in favor of considering this example as one of the earliest oghams in Scotland due to the fact that comparable scripts are ubiquitous in Ireland. Moreover, the stone's size and shape, and the positioning of the inscriptions' lettering and proportion of its strokes which is, as she notes <q>closest of all the Scottish examples to the Southern Irish norm</q> (ibid., 297).
  </div>

```

TX1

TX6

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

Florian Thiery / Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

153.—(No. VI).

At Chute Hall. Grit, 3' 4" × 1' 0" × 0' 7". Inscription on two diagonally opposed angles, up-down.

CCICAMINI MAQQI CATTINI

Of 4I, all but I¹ is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of CATTINI and the following A. The doubled initial C does not appear to be anything more than an engraver's freak: it would be a mistake to separate CCI from the rest of the names and to equate it to the always enclitic KOI. We shall see a similar beginning at Camp (177).

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p. 149

CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI

BALIG/6

Corpus: [Macalister/1897:11](#)

Refs: [Macalister/1945:153](#)

Site: [BALIG](#)

Discovery: recognised, 1782 Pelham, H.

History: According to Macalister/1945, 144, this stone was found 'in an ancient burial-ground, called Kilvickillane, on the shore of Smerwick Bay'. It was subsequently transferred in 1848 to Chute Hall, near Tralee.

Geology: Macalister/1945, 149: 'Grit'

Dimensions: 1.02 x 0.3 x 0.18 (converted from Macalister/1945)

Setting: unattach

Location: other
Macalister/1945, 145--147: 'this stone was found in an ancient burial-ground, called Kilvickillane, on the shore of Smerwick Bay...It was taken to his residence, Chute Hall, near Tralee'.

Form: plain

Condition: complete, some
Macalister/1945, 149, refers to some letters being chipped off the stone.

Folklore: none

Crosses: none

Decorations: no other decoration

References

- [Cuppige/etal/1986](#) 149 drawing concise discussion
- [Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 minor reference
- [Macalister/1945](#) 149 drawing concise discussion

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

via http://wajid.org/cispdb/stone/balig_6

Inscriptions

BALIG/6/1

Readings

Macalister, R.A.S. (1897): CCICAMINI MAQQICATTINI
Expansion:
CCICAMINI MAQQI CATTINI
[Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 reading only
[Macalister/1945](#) 149 reading only
[Ziegler/1994](#) 264 reading only

Cuppige, J. (1986): CCICAMINI MAQQI[C]C[A]TTINI
Expansion:
CCICAMINI MAQQI[C]C[A]TTINI
[Cuppige.etal/1986](#) 149 reading only

Notes

Orientation: vertical up down
Position: n/a; aris; n/a; undecorated
Incision: inc
Date: None published
Language: Goidelic (ogham)
Ling. Notes: none
Palaeography: none
Legibility: some

Macalister/1945, 149: 'Of 4l, all but 1l is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A. The doubled initial C does not appear to be anything more than an engraver's freak: it would be a mistake to separate CCI from the rest of the names and to equate it to the always enclitic KOI.'

Lines: 2
Carving errors: n
Doubtful: no

Names

- [Ciccamini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
- [Cattini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

References

- [Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 drawing concise discussion
- [Macalister/1945](#) 149 drawing concise discussion

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/version/2013/stone.php?lang=en&site=Ballinrannig&stone=153_Ballinrannig_VI
<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballinrannig-ogham-stone-2-88f32ed88497483da4d3607b6649d68e>

Go to Inscription

Ogham in 3D

Download Epidoc | URI https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153_Ballinrannig_VI

CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry

[Inscription](#) [Description](#) [3D View](#) [Map](#) [Epidoc](#)

National Monuments Service Record Number: KE942-057011.

Site Type
Burial ground and probable ecclesiastical site

Description
Site
"Civickillane/Cill Mhíic *Líleáir*: A large, grass-grown, sandy knoll, crowned by a single ogham stone, is located at the base of a small promontory on the S' shore of Smervick Harbour. It was here that a storm at the end of the 18th century exposed 7 ogham stones, a possible fragment of an ogham stone, a number of graves and quantities of bone, and the ruins of several houses (Windele 1838, 145; Chatterton 1839, 194). Windele's sketch of the site shows the ogham stones set out in a rough semi-circle on top of the mound with a slab-lined grave positioned nearby. Chatterton describes the houses as being beyond the mound nearer the sea. Windele interpreted these as the remains of an ancient village, but it has also been suggested that one of the structures, roughly 20 feet x 12 feet (6 x 3.7m), was a church (Curran no. 21). Lord Ventry removed 6 of the ogham stones from the site in the mid-19th century; nos. 1 to 4 now line the driveway to Burnham House/Colaiste Íde, between Dingle and Ventry, and nos. 5 and 6 are preserved in the grounds of Chute Hall near Tralee. Only no 7 is still preserved on the original site" (Cuppige 1986, 250-2).

Monument
"Grif", 1.02m x 0.30m x 0.18m (Converted from Macalister 1945, 149). Some damage evident at the top of the stone.

Text
The inscription is up-top-down, 'on two diagonally opposed angles... Of 4l [MAQO]l, but 11 is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A' (Macalister 1945, 149). It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorated CCICAMINI and the following formula word MAQO (represented by 'vac' below). This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also CIIC 119 Monastagart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by Molloy (2011, 290).

Transliteration
CCICAMINIVAC: MAQO[?] C[A]TTINI

Translation
of C? son of Caltne'

Commentary
• The father's name CATTINI (later Caltne) likewise occurs as the father's name in an inscription found at Ballintaggart (CIIC 157), a site also located in Corca Dhubhíne territory.

Locations
Found
Exposed by a storm at the end of the 18th century, along with 6 other ogham stones (Cuppige 1986, 250), in the lowland of Ballinrannig and barony of Corkaguiney. (GPS coordinates -10.388106, 52.178511)

Original
Find location probably original site

Last Recorded
In the mid 19th century this stone and CIIC 153 were moved by Lord Ventry to Chute Hall, near Tralee, where they remain today. The present location of this stone may be accessed via the National Monuments Service History www.archaeology.ie (GPS coordinates -9.642423, 52.275865)

History of Recording
First recognised in 1782 by Pitham and recorded by Vallancey (1804) in *Collectanea de Rebus Hibernicis* 6, 226 (Macalister 1945, 144). This stone was recorded for the Ogham in 3D project in 2017 by Helena Zacharias, a participant project, using Structure from Motion 3d technology.

References
• Bennett J. and Uí Shíbhígh B. (1995). *Ogham Stones of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 7-8.
• Cuppige, J. et al (1986). *Archaeological Survey of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 250-2.
• Macalister, R.A.S. (1945). *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, pp 144, 149.
• McManus, D. (1991). *A guide to ogham: Maynooth Monographs* 4, p. 108.

Websites and Online Databases
• Corca Dhubhíne 3d: www.corcadhubhine3d.ie
• <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballinrannig-ogham-stone-2-88f32ed88497483da4d3607b6649d68e>

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CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry
Site Type
Description
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Monument
Text
Transliteration
Translation
Commentary
Locations
Found
Original
Last Recorded
History of Recording
References
Websites and Online Databases

CIIC 153 / 153._Ballinrannig_VI (Ogham @ 3D Repository)

```
<div type="description" n="text">
  <head>Text</head>
  <p>The inscription is up-top-down, <q>on two diagonally opposed angles...
    Of 4I [MAQQI], all but I1 is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A</q> (<ref type="bibliog" target="#MAC1945">
      <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
        >149</biblScope></bibl></ref>. It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorate
    This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also <ref
      target="search.php?ciic=118"
    >CIIC 118</ref> Monataggart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by <ref
      type="bibliog" target="#MOF2011"><bibl><author>Moffat</author> (<date
        when="2011">2011</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
          >290</biblScope></bibl></ref>.
  </p>
</div>
```


Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

```
<div type="edition" xml:lang="ga">
  <head xml:lang="en">Transliteration</head>
  <ab>
    <persName><w lemma="CCICAMINI">CCICAMINI</w></persName><space></space>
    <w lemma="MAQI" type="formula">MAQ/Q<supplied reason="lost">/I</supplied></w>
    <persName><w lemma="CATTINI">C<supplied reason="lost">A</supplied>TTINI</w></persName>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="translation" xml:lang="en">
  <head>Translation</head>
  <ab><q>of C? son of Caitne</q></ab>
</div>
```


CIIC 153 as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

By **Megan Kasten**, OG(H)AM UK Postdoctoral Researcher

In May, Megan and Katherine 3D recorded ogham stones in Aberdeenshire, including this month's Ogham of the Month: Logie Elphinstone (S-ABD-002; [Canmore ID 1855](#)). Logie Elphinstone 2 is a pillar of an unusually pointed shape and measures 1.37m high and 0.46m wide. Like several of the Aberdeenshire ogham stones, it appears to be a reused prehistoric standing stone, formerly part of a stone circle (it was originally discovered with at least two other Pictish symbol stones, a fourth having been destroyed when reused in a kiln).

3D Model of Logie Elphinstone 2 using Meshlab's Radiance Scaling.

The stone is incised with two layers of Pictish symbols (the partially erased double-disc is visible under the clearer pair of Crescent-and-V-rod and Double-disc-and-Z-rod). Above the symbols are five ogham letters carved on a circular stem-line. The Buckquoy spindle whorl ([March 2022's Ogham of the month](#)) and the amber bead from Ennis ([I-CLA-003](#)) also have stemlines which are circular loops, but in those cases the objects are circular: this is a unique example on flat stone. It may be intended to recall the ogham-inscribed wooden hoops, or withies, referred to in Early Irish sagas as being left on pillar stones as a warning to passersby. The letters can be read QFTQU in a circle, or NFINU if reading in the other direction, but it is not clear in either case where one is meant to start. Perhaps the text is deliberately cryptic, like some of the fictional oghams described in the sagas.

Og(h)am of the Month Jun 2022: S-ABD-002 (LPHIN/1)

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Map

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Logie Elphinstone in CANMORE

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Logie Elphinstone

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Ogham Inscribed Stone (Pictish), Pictish Symbol Stone (Pictish)

Site Name Logie Elphinstone
Classification Ogham Inscribed Stone (Pictish), Pictish Symbol Stone (Pictish)
Alternative Name(s) Logie House Policies; Logie Elphinstone No. 2, Moor Of Carden
Canmore ID 18855
Site Number NJ72NW 7.02
NGR NJ 7034 2588
Datum OSG836 - NGR
Permalink <http://canmore.org.uk/site/18855>

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Logie Elphinstone in Sketchfab

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<publicationStmnt>
  <authority>OG(H)AM</authority>
  <idno type="filename">S-ABD-002</idno>
  <idno type="CIIC"/>
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  <availability>
    <licence target="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License</licence>
  </availability>
</publicationStmnt>

<sourceDesc>
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    <msIdentifier>
      <country>Scotland</country>
      <repository>
        <idno type="invNo"/>
      </msIdentifier>
    <msContent>
      <msItem>
        <textLang mainLang="und-Ogam">Undetermined language written in ogham script</textLang>
      </msItem>
    </msContent>
    <physDesc>
      <objectDesc>
        <supportDesc>
          <support><ref target="https://www.trove.scot/place/18855">Trove</ref> <idno type="Trove">18855</idno></support>
          <material type="stone">Granite</material>
          <objectType key="monument">Class I Pictish symbol stone</objectType>
          <dimensions unit="m">
            <height>1.37</height>
            <width>0.76</width>
            <depth>0.45</depth>
          </dimensions>
          <desc type="decoration">The lower two-thirds are occupied by a pair of Pictish symbols, a <rs type="decoration" key="PictishSymbol"> crescent-and-V rod over double-disc-and-Z rod</rs> (Forsyth 1996, 390). The carving of the symbols is <q>broader, deeper, and smoother</q> than the ogham carving, <q>but this may reflect nothing more than the larger scale of the former</q> (ibid. 391).</desc>
        </supportDesc>
        <condition>The monument is likely a prehistoric standing stone (blue granite) which was reused for the carving of Pictish symbols and an ogham inscription both of which are intact and well-preserved.</condition>
      </objectDesc>
      <layoutDesc>
        <layout type="other" reads="stamline circular">The ogham inscription is cut on a circular stem in the middle of the top third of the pointed pillar. The reading starts from the 10 o'clock position, as this is where the largest gap is located, and continues clockwise (Forsyth 1996, 394).</layout>
      </layoutDesc>
      <objectDesc>
        <handDesc>
          <handNote>The ogham inscription and symbols were <rs type="execution" key="pocked" ref="https://www.eagle-network.eu/voc/writing/10d/11.html"> pocked and rubbed</rs> smooth, a technique that is typical of Pictish Class I carvings (Forsyth 1996, 391). Strokes are generally evenly spaced and there are generous gaps between letters, though it is important to keep in mind the possibility of distortion due to the circular stem (ibid. 396). The number of strokes per letter is accepted as: 5, 3, 3, 5, 3.
          <height>The shortest letter strokes are 3cm long, the longest are 7cm, and the remainder vary between 4 and 6cm (ibid. 393).</height>
        </handNote>
      </handDesc>
      <physDesc>
        <history>
          <origin>
            <origPlace><placeName type="parish">Chapel Of Garioch</placeName>, <placeName type="county">Aberdeenshire</placeName>, <placeName type="country">Scotland</placeName>
            <geo>57.322500, -2.494167</geo>
            <note>National Grid Reference: NJ 7034 2588</note></origPlace>
            <origdate>
          </origin>
          <provenance type="found" when="1856">First mentioned by J Stuart in <date>1856</date>. This was one of four stones found lying on the ground on the Moor of Carden to the west of Logie Elphinstone House in or prior to about 1821. At that time the moor was planted and three of the stones were built into the enclosing wall, while the fourth (which is not known certainly to have been carved) was used as a floor slab in a kiln and <q>split by the heat and destroyed</q> (Stuart 1856, 4). The three symbol stones were subsequently removed from the wall and erected in the house grounds (Forsyth 1996, 385).
          </provenance>
          <provenance type="observed" when="2022-05-18">Recorded on the grounds of <placeName>Logie Elphinstone House</placeName>, to the west of the house at NJ 7033 2588, on <date>May 18th 2022</date>.
          </provenance>
        </history>
      </physDesc>
    </msDesc>
  </sourceDesc>
```

E22

E25

Logie Elphinstone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

```
<text>
  <body>
    <div type="edition" subtype="ogham" xml:lang="und-0gam" xml:space="preserve" resp="#LH">
      <ab>
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:clockwise"/>_+_
      </ab>
    </div>
    <div type="edition" subtype="transliteration" xml:lang="und-0gam" xml:space="preserve" resp="#LH">
      <ab>
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:clockwise"/>QFTQU TX1
      </ab>
    </div>
    <div type="apparatus">
      <listApp>
        <app n="1">
          <note>According to Forsyth (1996, 398), the lack of vowels <q>strongly suggests that the sequence is either encoded, or has no linguistic significance</q>.</note>
        </app>
        <app n="2">
          <note>There are two <q>clearly artificial</q> scores outside the stem beyond the first and third strokes of the second letter which might be intended as punctuation marks <q>added to differentiate group 2 from the strokes on either side</q> (Forsyth 1996, 395).</note> TX6
        </app>
      </listApp>
    </div>
    <div type="translation">
      <p>Logie is the shortest complete monumental ogham text in Scotland and as such cannot be readily interpreted (Forsyth 1996, 398). </p>
    </div>
    <div type="commentary">
      <p>The placement of the symbols suggests that the ogham was accounted for in the original design which further implies that the ogham relates to the same phase as the symbols, though it cannot be definitively proved. The stone is a palimpsest as there are visible remains of a partially-erased double-disc and Z-rod under the symbols; however, the overall layout strongly supports the assumption that the ogham relates to the second phase (Forsyth 1996, 391-2).</p>
    </div>
    <div type="bibliography">
      <listBibl>
        <bibl><ptr target="FOR1996"/>
          <citedRange>385-401</citedRange>
        </bibl>
        <bibl><ptr target="STU1856"/>
          <citedRange>4</citedRange>
        </bibl>
      </listBibl>
    </div>
  </body>
</text>
```

Logie Elphinstone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

Jupyter Python Minions for OG(H)AM

Make cool SPARQL visualisations

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q806167.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
    ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
    ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
    ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()

# Map 3: Density map with normalized values
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Output

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

A Linked Open Data Plugin for QGIS

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhefter Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kin region (KinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sfMultiPolygon
- sfPoint
- sfPolygon
- wgs84_posSpatialThing

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: /rest/xyz/xyz/ (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Example queries: [Please select]

Press CTRL + S to export to autoquery.txt

Gezeichnete Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: Engl

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

Item	label	geo	county	count
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000019	Ballybrock (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.07111 52.02644)"^^geo:wkt	"Cork" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Cumshinga (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(7.44856 52.14856)"^^geo:wkt	"Waterford" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000021	Bullinbeggar (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(10.05111 52.2727)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Killeshale East / Killeshale (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(6.74222 52.07044)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockbay (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(7.6 52.11889)"^^geo:wkt	"Waterford" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000019	Bullinbeggy (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(10.84611 52.27611)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000077	Coolemore (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(9.64278 52.06111)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000073	Colbinstown / Killeen Cormac (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(6.75689 52.05111)"^^geo:wkt	"Kildare" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000030	Ballyhank (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.60833 51.83611)"^^geo:wkt	"Cork" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000175	Knockanavee (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.79472 51.86856)"^^geo:wkt	"Cork" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000210	Whitefield (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(9.70556 52.08556)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000114	Kilgrovan (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.54972 52.09556)"^^geo:wkt	"Waterford" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000183	Monatagarr (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.77944 51.97444)"^^geo:wkt	"Cork" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000208	Rockfield / Laham (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(9.63667 52.12889)"^^geo:wkt	"Kerry" @en	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS40000209	Roovee More (Ogham Site) @en	"POINT(8.78417 51.88667)"^^geo:wkt	"Cork" @en	1

N4O KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?geo ?label WHERE {
2   ?item rdfs:label ?label .
3   ?item <http://ontology.ogham.link/within> <http://lod.ogham.link/data/GSD3000003> .
4   ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
5   ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
6 }
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (11) FeatureCollections Geo

- Barony
- Location
- Place
- gsp:Feature
- ns1:Barony
- ns1:GeographicLocation
- ns1:Island
- ns1:OghamSite
- ns1:Province
- sf:MultiPolygon
- sf:Point

Ogham Stones in the Province Munster

Ogham Stones in the Province Munster

Go raibh maith agat! Thx!

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